

Adaptation Trials of Three Varieties of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) in the Edaphoclimatic Conditions of Lwiro, South Kivu, Eastern DRC

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Abstract

The DRC's production is not enough to cover the country's needs and it has to import large quantities. Abnormal situation when it is known that the DRC, taking into account its resources in irrigation water and arable land, should be the granaries of cereal production for Africa. The problem lies, among other things, in the lack of infrastructure, agricultural inputs, and in particular high-yielding seeds.

This work had the objective of evaluating three new wheat varieties in order to study their agronomic performance under the edapho-climatic conditions of Lwiro. To achieve this, a test was installed at the Center for Research in Natural Sciences, in the experimental field of the Agricultural Entomology Laboratory. It was carried out in the period from March to July of the year 2022. The sketch is a completely randomized design with three repetitions having a total of 12 treatments.

The recovery rate is considered favorable because it exceeds 90%; all the varieties have a medium cycle since it oscillates around 120 to 150 days. About the growth and yield parameters, the results revealed differences between varieties under study. Except for the number of tillers for which the analysis of variance did not show any significant differences, for the height of the plants (the averages of which vary between 53-77 cm) and the number of leaves per plant (the averages vary between 12 and 25); the KIMA variety was better compared to MBALALIZI and LUBERO. For the number of grains per ear, the weight of 1,000 grains as well as the yield, the KIMA variety still proved to be the most adapted to the environment with productions of more than 3 T/ha (3.22 T/ha) of the homogeneous group A, followed by MBALALIZI (2.51 T/ha) and finally by LUBERO (2.30 T/ha) constituting the homogeneous group B. Thus, the KIMA variety would seem to be indicated for the promotion of wheat in the region.

Keywords: *Wheat, adaptation, varieties, Lwiro, South Kivu, Eastern DRC 5.*

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Introduction

Cereals occupy an essential place in the agricultural system on a global scale. They are considered as a main source of human and animal nutrition (Slama et al., 2005). They provide 57% of protein consumed against 23% provided by tubers and legumes as well as 20% by products of animal origin (Gcema et al., 2011). From the year 1980, their consumption in developing countries exceeded that of developed countries and now represents 61% of world consumption; they are the main staple foods in these regions or in less economically developed regions. In 2014, cereal production is estimated at 2 532 million tons (Merabti, 2015).

The soft wheat consumption and production occupy a privileged place in the world compared to other cereals; its annual production is about 600 million tons (Ricroch et al., 2011). Wheat is the most consumed with rice by humans, providing it with a significant calorific intake (Zohary and Hopf, 2000). Its importance goes beyond the traditional role considered as food (Ammar, 2015). Wheat alone provides more protein than poultry, pork and beef combined. Corn, rice and wheat are even the source of 6% of the fat we eat (FAO 2015; United States Department of Agriculture 2015).

In Africa, especially in Algeria, cereal growing occupies an area of between 3 and 3.3 million hectares, 41% of this area is reserved for wheat (Madr, 2008). Algerian local production remains modest compared to consumption needs which are increasing rapidly due to the doubling of the number of consumers and the increase in consumption by households (Rachedi, 2003). This imbalance between supply and demand ranks Algeria among the world's leading importers. It is the world's third largest importer of cereals after Brazil and Egypt. As an indication, the quantity of wheat imported for the 2005-2006 season reached 5.5 million tonnes (Kellou, 2008). While production for the same season was 17.7 million quintals, this production fell to 8.1 million quintals in 2008 (Madr, 2009). The low level of technicality of the farmers associated with the poor preparation of the soil, the insufficient protection of crops against predators, diseases and weeds and the low level of use of inputs explains the low yields obtained (Felliachi, 2000).

Regarding to the DRC's wheat production which is similar to the known African Countries situation, wheat yield is not enough to cover the country's needs and it has to import large quantities (Amuli 2015). From 1996 to 1998, yields recorded using varieties imported from France and Italy oscillated between 200 and 400 kg/ha, depending on the agro-ecological zone, between 1600 to 2500 m altitude (Inspection Provinciale d'Agriculture, 2000; Payne, 2000; Bishweka, 1999). The DRC, in Kinshasa, via the companies ORGAMAN, CONGO FUTUR, SOCIMEX, imports a lot of dry products, especially wheat flour and rice; these imports are estimated at more than 100,000 tons of wheat flour; this despite the customs duty of 35.60% which affects imports of wheat flour (Tollens 2003). Abnormal situation when it is known that the DRC, taking into account its resources in irrigation water and arable land, should be the granaries of cereal production for Africa (Amuli 2015).

The South Kivu situation is such that the population lives mainly from agriculture: 51% of households say they live from agriculture compared to 28.9% who say they live from livestock (PAM, 2019). Although agriculture remains the main subsistence activity of households in the province, the rate of dependence on food from neighboring countries (Uganda, Tanzania, Rwanda and Burundi) remains high, more than

$\frac{3}{4}$ (i.e. 78.7%), except for cassava and bananas (PAM, 2019). Only 14.8% of food comes from peasant subsistence production (PAM, 2019) ; this was reinforced with the COVID-19 crisis, where movement restrictions and the closure of borders with neighboring countries led to a low availability of food products in the area, causing the price of certain foodstuffs and household products to rise (IPC DRC, 2020).

For some authors, the problem is essentially technical and political because traditional cereal cultivation is inefficient and suffers from a lack of infrastructures, agricultural inputs, and in particular high-yield seeds/varieties (SENASA, 2009). Drivers' factors of investment in varietal innovations include the need to improve yield potential, resistance/tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses, and nutritional and processing quality (Atack et al., 2008; Lantican et al., 2005)

This paper explores the hypothesis that the three varieties will behave differently in the climatic conditions of Lwiro. The overall aim is to evaluate the productivity of these three varieties in order to study their agronomic performance.

Location, Materials and Method

Location

Figure 1. Map of Location of the Trail at the Entomological Laboratory Concession at CRSN/LWIRO; (a) Positioning of the province of South Kivu on the DRC map; (b) Positioning of the trial on the map of the Kabare Territory map in South Kivu province; (c) Location of the trial in the CRSN Lwiro concession in Kabare

The experiment was carried out at the experimental site of the Agricultural Entomology Laboratory of CRSN-Lwiro located at $28^{\circ} 48' 43''$ E, $2^{\circ} 14' 15''$ S; at an altitude of 1750 m on the western shores of Lake Kivu, 40 km northeast of the city of Bukavu, in the territory of Kabare, Province of South Kivu, Democratic Republic of Congo (Munyuli, 2003).

Table 1. Average Values of Temperature and Rainfall Covering Season B 2022

Month	February	March	April	May	June	July
Rainy days	11	14	16	8	2	3
Quantity in mm	137.6	146.7	234.8	170.2	23	59.3
Temperature (°C)	18.6	19.5	19.1	18.8	17.9	19.1

Source: CRSN/Lwiwo; Weather station, 2022

The results in table 1 show the amounts of rainfall and the temperature during cropping season B of the year 2022 (from February to July 2022). The largest amounts of rain were recorded in April with 234.8 mm of water in 16 rainy days while the month of June recorded the lowest amounts of rain, 23 mm of water. The temperature is almost uniformly distributed throughout the period of the experiment and therefore no spectacular variation has been observed.

According to DSRP 2005, the climate of the study area is tropical tempered by altitude. Average annual rainfall is around 1,100 mm/year with regional variations of 800 to 1,500 mm/year (FAO, 2012). Average annual temperatures vary between 11 and 25°C (PAM, 2019).

Materials

Three varieties of wheat certified by INERA MULUNGU (Kima, Mbalalizi and Lubero) and some field equipment (GPS for geographical data; rulers, strings for measuring land areas and plant height; hoes, tridents for plowing; secateurs for harvesting, etc.)

Table 2. Characteristics of the Varieties under Study (Kima, Mbalalizi and Lubero)

Varieties	Lubero	Kima	Mbalalizi
Number of lifting days	7	7	7
Color of leaves	Green	Green	Green light
Lodging resistance	Yes	Yes	Yes
Number of tillers after 20 days	5	6	7
Appearance of the last leaf	60	67	70
Earing (in days)	65	72	75
Flowering (in days)	78	80	83
Average plant height in cm	72	90	88
Average ear length in cm	14	15	12
Physiological maturity (in days)	150	165	170
Number of grains per ear	47	52	55
Average 1 000 grains weight in g	40	47	45
Yield in T/ha	1.45	2.05	1.9

Source: INERA, 2018

From Table 2, it is noted that all the varieties under study have a strong resistance to lodging, are green in color and their rate of emergence occurs 7 days after sowing. As regards physiological maturity average (which occurs between 120-146 days), 1 000 grain weight (varying between 40-47g) and yield in T/ha (1.45-2.05); the KIMA variety is ahead of the two other varieties under study (MBALALIZI and LUBERO) which rank second and third respectively.

Table 3. Analysis Results of the Soil Sample from the Experimental Site

pH in water	% C	% N	% C/N	Ca (ppm)	Mg (ppm)	CEC meq/100g
7,3	3,95	0,23	9,03	38	17	16,65

Source: INERA, 2018

pH in water

From the results in Table 3, it is shown that the experimental soil is neutral because it is between 6.6 and 7.3 (Agriculture & Agroalimentaire Canada, 2022). This means that the experimental soil is of good quality for most crops including wheat.

Organic carbon, Total nitrogen and C/N ratio

The contents obtained were 3.95 in organic carbon and 0.23 in total nitrogen, which means that the soils were rich in carbon than in nitrogen, this implies according to (Kyela, 2011) that the organic matter found on the site was largely made up of undecomposed or poorly decomposed woody elements (C/N ratio=17.17; this ratio is very high because it is between 15 and 20).

For the CEC, in organic soils, this is high because it is between 15 and 25. According to LANO, 2016, this means that the experimental soil has a certain capacity to store sufficient mineral elements (exchangeable cations) that can be available to the plant.

Table 4. Maximum Water Requirements per Phase of Soft Wheat

Varieties Phases	Seedling-emergence	Tillering	Rising	Heading	Maturation	Total	
<i>Water requirements/ phase (mm)</i>	5,93	53,91	77,75	167,30	101,89	406,79	
Kima	Number of days	20	40.5	28.5	33	43	165
	ETM (mm)	93.5	189.4	133.3	154.32	201	771.6
Lubero	Number of days	18	37	26	30	39	150
	ETM (mm)	84.2	189.4	121.6	140.3	182.4	771.6
Mbalalizi	Number of days	20	42	29.5	34	44.5	170
	ETM (mm)	93.5	196.4	138	159	208	771.6

Source: Kirad & Boubekeur 2020

It can be seen that for all phases (wheat growth and yield) complete satisfaction was achieved because the quantities of rainfall recorded were sufficient and regular. The total rainfall recorded during the cycle is 771.6 mm. It is considered very satisfactory because the water needs of the crop vary between 400 and 650 mm (Moule, 1980).

Methods

Experimental design

The sketch is a completely randomized design. This sketch that represents the experiment is such that the first block is the experiment and the 3 blocks are the repetitions. Block numbers and plots of the first block were randomly assigned. The treatments are: T1: Lubero Variety; T2: Mbalalizi Variety and T3: Kima Variety.

The plots were spaced 0.5 m apart and the blocks 1 m apart. In total, the experiment had 12 plots and 4 blocks. The experimental field had as a cultural precedent, an experimental trial of different varieties of Ipomoea batatas.

Figure 2. Experimental Design

Conduct of the Trial

The manual plowing was carried out with the hoe; the delimitation of the plot was measured by the decameter and the plots of the seeding line by the wires. Direct sowing was carried out on 04/03/2022 for all plots and all blocks that contained all varieties. Weeding was done every 15 days after noticing significant competition between weeds and the crop. Plant spacing was the same on all plots, 30 cm x 25 cm, with 4 seeds per pocket.

Parameters Observed

- **Lifting:** the emergence rate was achieved two weeks after sowing, i.e. exactly on 18/03/2022 directly followed by the refilling of voids. Out of a total of 3,840 seeds sown for all varieties, it turns out that 81 seeds of variety (T3) did not germinate, 73 seeds of variety (T2), 54 seeds of (T1). A total of 208 seeds did not germinate, i.e. 5.42%. The emergence rate is therefore 94.58%, which indicates that the seed was of good quality.
- **Height of plants, number of tillers, and number of leaves per plant:** all measurements were made one and a half months after sowing. The height of the plants was carried out from the collar of the plant to the apical meristem of the plant. The plants (10 plants per plot) were taken randomly without taking into account the border plants. These parameters provide information on the resistance to lodging of plants and the behavior of the plant on growth. The measurement of the height number of tillers and leaves was taken two times and this until before flowering. Sampling were done:
 - o for the first time, 6 weeks after sowing,
 - o for the second time, 8 weeks after sowing.
- **Yield:** performance parameters are:

- Number of spikelets per panicle (number of grains per panicle) : manual count
- Weight of 1 000 grains : by precision balance
- Yield is calculate with the formula :

$$Yd_{est} = (NEM*NGE*WTG)/100 \quad (1)$$

with Yd_{est} : Yield estimated; NEM: Number of ears/ m^2 ; NGE: Number of grains/ear; WTG: Weight of thousand grains

- Statistical analyzes were performed using R software (R Studio) version 4.2.1

Results

The height growth of wheat plants two months after sowing is represented by the figure 3.

Figure 3. Height Growth of Wheat Plants Two Months after Sowing

From the results in fig 3, it follows that at the 5% threshold, there is a significant difference between the different varieties under study. This means that the height of the plants in the study area is different from one variety to another. After the Comparison of plant height averages, it appears two homogeneous groups; the variety T3 (KIMA) recorded the greatest values of the height of the wheat plants while the variety T1 (LUBERO) has the lowest average value of the heights of the plants. Variety T2 (MBALALIZI) is intermediate to both classes. The next figure below shows the number of tillers emitted by wheat two months after sowing.

Figure 4. Number of Tillers Emitted by Wheat Two Months after Sowing

From fig 4, it is shown that there is not any significant difference in the treatments used. This means that the tillers are not different from one variety to another. The next figure represents the number of leaves emitted by wheat two months after sowing.

Figure 5. Number of Leaves Emitted by Wheat Two Months after Sowing

From the results in fig 5, it follows that at the 5% threshold, there is a significant difference between the different varieties under study. This means that the height of the plants in the study area is different from one variety to another. After the Comparison of plant leaves number averages, it appears two homogeneous groups, the variety T3 (KIMA) recorded the greatest values of the leaves number of the wheat plants while the varieties T1 (LUBERO) and T2 (MBALALIZI) are in the same homogenous class (b). The next figure represents production of wheat grains per panicle.

Figure 6. Production of Wheat Grains per Panicle Throughout the All Season

From the results in fig 6, it follows that at the 5% threshold, there is a high significant difference between the different varieties under study. This means that the grains of the panicle are different from one variety to another. After the comparison of the means there are two distinct individualized classes; the variety T3 (KIMA) recorded the greatest values of the height of the wheat plants while the variety T1 (LUBERO) has the lowest average value of the heights of the plants. Variety T2 (MBALALIZI) is intermediate to both classes. The next figure represents the production of wheat thousand grains weight.

Figure 7. Production of Wheat Thousand Grains Weight Throughout the All Season

From the results in fig 7, it follows that there is significant difference between the different varieties under study). After mean comparison, the results show that there are two distinct individualized classes; the varieties T3 (KIMA) and T2 (MBALALIZI) recorded the greatest values of 1000 grains weight averages and constitute the homogeneous class A while the variety T1 (LUBERO) has the lowest average value

of 1000 grains weight of plants and constitutes the homogeneous class B . The next figure represents the production of wheat yield in tons per hectare.

Figure 8. Production of Wheat Yield in Tons per Hectare Throughout the All Season

The results ANOVA show that there is a very highly significant difference between the different varieties studied ($P: 0,000341$). This means that the yield of the plants in the study area is very highly different from one variety to another. After men comparison, the results show that there are two distinct individualized classes; the varies T3 (KIMA) recorded the greatest values of average yields in T/ha and constitutes the homogeneous class A while the varieties T2 (MBALALIZI) and T1 (LUBERO) have the lowest average of yields in T/ha of plants and constitutes the homogeneous class B. The difference between the most and the least profitable varieties is about 0.9 t/ha. This is impressive and justifies the reason why the differences are very highly significant between the varieties under study.

Discussion

The results of the analysis, for the growth parameters, indicate that for the three varieties under study, the differences are significant at all levels of comparison except for the number of tillers per plant where the differences were not detected in the study area. This demonstrates that different varieties have different potentials. This supports the ideas of several authors who claim that varieties and cultivars within plant species differ in their growth and development, and that these differences are attributable to the morphological, physiological and biochemical processes of plants and their interaction with climate, soil and any other practices integrated into the cropping system (Magrini et al. & Serge et al., 2016).

According to Lounes & Guerfi 2010 ; Serge et al., 2016; the yield is 1.92 tons per hectare which is too low compared to the results in the study area while according to Benbelkacem & Kellou 2000; the average yield per hectare is 3.77 tons. This corresponds to the best variety (KIMA) that we had under study whose yield was around 3.22 T/ha. This is explained by the quality of soil preparation and its humidity as well as its physical properties, its altitude adapted to the varieties under study. The root depth is variable, depending on tillage and soil moisture, 50% of the total weight of the roots are between 0 to 25 cm, 10% between 20 to 50 cm but they can reach 1m to 1.2m in very deep soil (Soltner, 1980; Togun & Akanbi

2003). The most important advantage of being deep soil is that it facilitates the full development of the root system (Prat et Clement, 1971).

Added to this are the favorable climatic conditions (rainfall and sunshine) during the experimentation. According to (Kirad & Boubekeur, 2020), the daily water requirements of wheat cultivation are 0.32 to 1.38 mm per day during the initial phase then increase to 5.57 mm per day at the flowering stage. It was recorded daily amounts of rain of about 5 mm throughout the period of the experimentation. It can be seen that for all phases (wheat growth and yield) water complete satisfaction was achieved because the quantities of rainfall recorded were sufficient and regular. The total rainfall recorded during the cycle is 771.6 mm. It is considered very satisfactory because the water needs of the crop vary between 400 and 650 mm (Moule, 1980).

Conclusion

This work had the objective of evaluating three new varieties in order to study their agronomic performance under the edapho-climatic conditions of Lwiro. To achieve this, trial was installed at the Center for Research in Natural Sciences, in the experimental field of the Agricultural Entomology Laboratory. It was carried out from March to July 2022, season B. the experimental design is a completely randomized design with three repetitions having a total of 12 treatments.

At the end of the trial, the following observations were made:

- The recovery rate is considered favorable because it exceeds 90%; all the varieties have a medium cycle since it oscillates around 120 to 150 days.
- About the growth and yield parameters, the result revealed differences between varieties under study. Except for the number of tillers for which the analysis of variance did not show any significant differences, for the height of the plants (the averages of which vary between 53-77 cm) and the number of leaves per plant (the averages vary between 12 and 25); the KIMA variety was better compared to MBALALIZI and LUBERO.
- For the number of grains per ear, the weight of 1,000 grains as well as the yield, the KIMA variety still proved to be the most adapted to the environment with productions of more than 3 T/ha (3.22 T/ha) of the homogeneous group A, followed by MBALALIZI (2.51 T/ha) and finally by LUBERO (2.30 T/ha) constituting the homogeneous group B. Thus, the KIMA variety would seem to be indicated for the promotion of wheat in the region

References

- Agriculture et agroalimentaire Canada. (2022). Système d'information sur les sols du Canada. Retrieved from <http://sis.agr.gc.ca/>
- Ammar, M. (2014). *Organisation de la chaîne logistique dans la filière Céréales en Algérie, états des lieux et perspective*. Thèse de doctorat de Ciheam Montpellier.
- Amuli. (2015). *Comparaison de deux techniques de gestion intermittente d'eau sur le rendement des cinq variétés de riz irrigué à Kiringye dans la plaine de la Ruzizi, mémoire inédit*. UCB, pp. 51.
- Atack, J., Coclanis, P., & Grantham, G. (2009). Creating Abundance: Biological Innovation and American Agricultural Development—An appreciation and research agenda. *Explorations in Economic History*, 46, 160-167. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eeh.2008.11.001>

- Benbelkacem, A., & Kellou, K. (2001). Evaluation du progrès génétique chez quelques variétés de lé dur (*Triticum Turgidum* L. Var durum) cultivées en Algérie. *CIHEAM, série A*, 105-110.
- Bishweka, A. (1999). La culture du froment en Afrique Centrale (Sud-Kivu). *Recherches africaines*, 4, 99-112.
- DSRP. (2005). *Monographie de la province du Sud-Kivu*. Kinshasa, RDC: Ministère du Plan.
- FAO. (2012). AQUASTAT: Système mondial d'information sur l'eau et l'agriculture. Retrieved from <https://www.fao.org/aquastat/fr/>
- FAO. (2015). FAOSTAT. Base de données statistiques en ligne: Bilans alimentaires. Retrieved from <http://faostat.fao.org>
- Felliachi, K. (2000). Programme de développement de la céréaliculture en Algérie. *Proceedings du symposium BLE 2000, enjeux et strategies*.
- Gcema, M. (2011). *Contribution à l'étude de l'activité antifongique et Antimycotoxinogène des extraits méthanoliques et aqueux des graines de citrullus Colocynthis sur la croissance de quelques moisissures d'altération de blé tendre Stocké* (doctoral dissertation). Université Kasdi Merbah-Ouargla, option : microbiologie appliquée.
- INERA. (2018). Fiches techniques de classification et de suivi des variétés de blé.
- INERA. (2019). Laboratoire de Pédologie de l'INERA-MULUNGU
- Inspection provinciale d'agriculture. (2000). *Rapport de l'inspection agricole de la province du Sud-Kivu, R.D. Congo*. Rapport pour l'exercice de l'année 1996 à l'année 2000. Bukavu.
- IPC, DRC. (2020). *Analyse IPC de l'insécurité alimentaire aigue, situation par province*. Publié en.
- Kellou, R. (2008). *Analyse du marché algérien du blé dur et les opportunités d'exportation pour les céréaliers français dans le cadre du pôle de compétitivité Quali-Méditerranée : le cas des coopératives Sud Céréales, groupe coopératif Occitan et Audecoop*. Master of science. Montpellier: CIHEAM-IAMM, série Thèse et Master.
- Kirad, K. & Boubekour, F. (2020). *Comportement de quelques variétés de blé tendre dans la zone semi-aride du Haut Chéiff*. Thèse DUEA.
- Kyela. (2011). *Utilisation des composts de biodéchets ménagers pour l'amélioration de la fertilité des sols acides de la province de Kinshasa en République Démocratique du Congo*. Dissertation originale présentée en vue de l'obtention du grade de Docteur en sciences.
- LANO. (2016). Laboratoire Agronomique Normand. Retrieved from <http://lano.asso.fr/web/capacitedechangecationique.html>
- Lantican, M.A., Dubin, H.J., & Morris, M.L. (2005). *Impacts of international wheat breeding research in the developing world, 1988-2002*. Mexico: CIMMYT.
- Maamri, K. (2018). *Stabilité du critère de la discrimination du carbone isotopique en relation avec le poids spécifique de la feuille drapeau chez quelques variétés de blé dur cultivées en milieu semi-aride*. Mémoire de magister. Faculté SNV. UFA, Sétif.
- Maamri, K., (2011). *Stabilité du critère de la discrimination du carbone isotopique en relation avec le poids spécifique de la feuille drapeau chez quelques variétés de blé dur cultivées en milieu semi-aride*. Mémoire de magister. Faculté SNV. UFA, Sétif.
- MADR. (2009). *Statistiques agricoles: superficies et production*. Ed. MADR (Ministère de l'Agriculture et du Développement Rural), Alger.

- Magrini, M.-B., Triboulet, P., & Bedoussac, L. (2013). Pratiques agricoles innovantes et logistique des coopératives agricoles. Une étude ex-ante sur l'acceptabilité de cultures associées blé dur-légumineuses. *Economie rurale*, 338, 25-45. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4000/economierurale.4145>
- Merabti, R. (2015). *Blé dur fermenté le mzeiet : étude du nouveau procédé de fermentation A l'extérieur du matmor et caractérisation de l'écosystème (interactions du microbiote avec La matrice)*. Thèse de doctorat. Institut de la nutrition, de l'alimentation et des technologies agro-alimentaires (i.n.a.t.a.a). Université des frères mentouri-constantine.
- Moule, C. (1980). *Bases scientifiques et techniques de la production des principales espèces de grande culture en France*, Ed. Miason Rustique, Paris.
- Moumni, L. (2013). Quantification de la contrainte hydrique chez le blé dur (*Triticum durum* Desf) en milieu semi-aride.
- Munyuli Bin, M. (2003). Effet de différentes poudres végétales sur l'infestation des semences de légumineuses et de céréales au cours de la conservation au Kivu, (République Démocratique du Congo). *Note de recherche; Cahiers Agricultures*, 12, 23-31.
- Ndjadi, S.S., Mirindi, B.M., Musafiri, P., Basimine, G.C., Lwahamire, E.C. & Basengere, E.B. (2016) Evaluation of the Productivity of Seven Varieties of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) through Integrated Soil Fertility Management in Kaziba, South Kivu, DR Congo. *Field Actions Science Reports*, 9, 11.
- PAM. (2019). *Analyse de la sécurité alimentaire en situation d'urgence (EFSA-Emergency Food Security Assessment) au Sud-Kivu*. Rapport final.
- Payne, T. (2000). *Impact of maize and wheat research in Eastern and Central Africa: Results of recent studies*. ASARECA/Agriforum.
- Prats et Clement, M. (1971). *Les céréales*, 13ème édition collection sciences et technique agricole.
- Rachedi, M.F. (2003). Les céréales en Algérie : problématique et option de réforme. *Céréaliculture*, 38, 6-9.
- Ricroch, A., Dattée, Y. & Fellous, M. (2011). *Biotechnologie végétale In: environnement, alimentation, santé*. (eds) du Vuibert. Paris.
- SENASAEM. (2008). Règlement de la production, du contrôle et de la certification des semences des principales cultures vivrières et maraichères.
- Slama, A., Ben Salem, M., Ben Naceur, M., & Zid, E.D. (2005). *Les céréales en Tunisie: production, effet de la sécheresse et mécanismes de résistance*. Institut national de la recherche agronomique de Tunisie (Inrat). Univ. Elmanar. Tunisie.
- Soltner. (1980). *Les grandes productions végétales, collections de sévices des techniques agricoles*.
- Soltner. (1988). *Les bases de la production végétale*. Troisième édition.
- Togun, A. O., & Akanbi, W. B. (2003). Comparative Effectiveness of Organic-Based Fertilizer To Mineral Fertilizer on Tomato Growth and Fruit Yield. *Compost Science & Utilization*, 11(4), 337-342. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1065657X.2003.10702143>
- Tollens, E. (2003). *L'état actuel de la sécurité alimentaire en RD Congo: diagnostic et perspectives*. Working Paper, n: 77, Département d'Economie Agricole et de l'Environnement, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven.
- United States Department of Agriculture. (2015). *World agricultural supply and demand estimates*. Washington
- Zohary, D., & Hopf, M. (2000). *Domestication of plants in the old world: the origin and spread of cultivated plants in West Asia, Europe, and the Nile Valley*. Oxford University Press.

